

NOTES

Some Transition Metal Complexes of Benzene Substituted-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thiones

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IN continuation of our studies on the metal complexes of thioquinazolones¹ we report here Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{III} complexes of 6-bromo-3-n-propyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HBPQT), 6-bromo-3-n-butyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HBBQT), 6-bromo-3-allyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HBAQT), 6-bromo-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HBQT), 6-iodo-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HIQT) and 6,8-dibromo-3-phenyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thione (HDBPQT).

R = H/alkyl/phenyl ; X = Br/I ; X' = H/Br

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported in the literature¹⁻³. The complexes were prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of cupric nitrate/nickel nitrate/hexammine cobaltic chloride in water and the corresponding ligand in alcohol/acetone/DMF. For the preparation of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, pH of the solution was maintained at 6.5 using acetate buffer. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes formed immediately after mixing the two solutions while Co^{III} complexes formed on refluxing the solution. The complexes were filtered and washed with water. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes were insoluble in common organic solvents but slightly soluble in DMF. They were purified by washing with hot methanol/acetone in which the ligands are soluble. The Co^{III} complexes were insoluble in methanol and acetone but were soluble in CHCl₃, CCl₄ and DMF. They were recrystallised from CHCl₃ to get shining green crystals.

Elemental analysis and room temperature magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) data are presented in Table 1.

Molar conductance was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Electronic spectra were

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			μ_{eff} B.M.
	N	S	M	
Cu(BPQT) ₂	8.40 (8.49)	9.65 (9.72)	9.68 (9.63)	2.19
Cu(BBQT) ₂	7.98 (8.14)	9.37 (9.30)	9.31 (9.24)	2.19
Cu(BAQT) ₂	8.46 (8.54)	9.52 (9.63)	9.35 (9.65)	2.10
Ni(BPQT) ₂	8.38 (8.55)	9.77 (9.79)	8.93 (8.97)	3.8
Ni(BBQT) ₂	8.07 (8.20)	9.33 (9.39)	8.51 (8.59)	3.78
Ni(BAQT) ₂	8.51 (8.60)	9.73 (9.85)	9.01 (9.02)	3.9
Ni(DBPQT) ₂	6.30 (6.36)	7.07 (7.28)	6.48 (6.66)	3.83
Ni(IQT) ₂	8.33 (8.42)	9.60 (9.64)	8.82 (8.83)	3.81
Co(BQT) ₂	10.08 (10.16)	11.82 (11.63)	7.00 (7.12)	0.62
Co(BPQT) ₂	8.65 (8.79)	9.98 (10.04)	6.06 (6.10)	0.42
Co(BBQT) ₂	8.21 (8.44)	9.54 (9.66)	5.88 (5.93)	0.54
Co(BAQT) ₂	8.74 (8.87)	10.08 (10.15)	6.13 (6.23)	0.48

*Temp. = 300 K.

recorded on a Beckman DU7 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman spectrophotometer, epr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes in powder were recorded on a Varian E4 spectrometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond to ML₂ and that of the Co^{III} complexes correspond to ML₃ stoichiometry. Molar conductance of the complexes were found to be less than 10 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complexes were found to be 2.1–2.9 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron. The Ni^{II} complexes have magnetic moments in the range 3.78–3.9 B.M. suggesting a tetrahedral structure⁴. The Co^{III} complexes have magnetic moments in the range 0.48–0.54 B.M. due to T.I.P.⁵.

In the electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes three bands observed at 550, 640 and 670 nm are characteristic of square-planar or distorted octahedral Cu^{II} complexes, which are due to the transitions ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ respectively. In the case of the Ni^{II} complexes one band observed at ~ 610 nm is assigned to the transition ${}^3T_{1(P)} \leftarrow {}^3T_{1(F)}$ in T_d symmetry. The Co^{III}

complexes show two weak bands at 485 and 640 nm due to the transitions ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ respectively.

In the ir spectra of the ligands, a band observed at 3200 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ is absent in the spectra of the complexes. So the NH moiety was deprotonated due to complex formation. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band observed at $\sim 1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand remained unaltered in the complexes suggesting that oxygen is not taking part in the complex formation. The spectra of the complexes show two new bands due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ at 1610 and 690 cm^{-1} respectively. This new $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band and the change of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ of the ligand to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ in the complexes suggest that the complex formation occurred through the sulphur atom. Probably the complex formation occurred through a tautomeric change :

as the ir frequency changes demand. $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ bands are observed at 550 and 380 cm^{-1} .

The values of g_{\parallel} (2.14–2.2) and g_{\perp} (2.08–2.09) were calculated from the anisotropic spectra which are typical of monomeric Cu^{II} complexes. $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ suggests an elongated tetragonal geometry and the unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital⁷.

Nmr spectra of the n-butyl derivative (Co^{III}) shows a triplet at $\delta 1.7$ for the methyl group. The two middle CH_2 signals are complex and are centred at $\delta 2.0$ and 2.3 . The CH_2 group attached to the nitrogen atom of the quinazolone ring is deshielded giving a triplet at $\delta 4.8$. Signals due to the aromatic protons are observed at $\delta 7.6$ – 8.3 . The aromatic proton at position-5 is deshielded by the bromine atom and the carbonyl oxygen; hence the extreme signal at $\delta 8.3$ is considered to be due to this proton. The allyl derivative shows a signal due to CH_3 at $\delta 1.8$. The quartet due to CH adjacent to the CH_3 group is observed at $\delta 5.4$. The other CH group shows a resonance at $\delta 6.0$ because the nucleus is deshielded by nitrogen. The aromatic proton signals are observed at $\delta 7.8$ – 8.5 . In addition to the aromatic proton signals, the n-propyl derivative shows signals at $\delta 1.75$ (t, CH_3) signal (complicated) due to $-\text{CH}_2-$ at $\delta 2.2$ (CH_2) and 4.7 (t, CH_2 attached the nitrogen atom). The signal due to NH is always difficult to identify because of the quadrupole moment of nitrogen and the exchange of this proton. However, a peak observed at $\delta 3.2$ in the ligand is absent in the spectrum of the complexes and is assigned to NH proton. Its absence in the complex shows that the coordination to Co^{III} has taken place through nitrogen atom.

Thus in Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{III} complexes of 6-bromo-3-alkyl-4-oxoquinazoline-2-thiones the four-membered ring formed on complexation is quite

stable. X-Ray study of stable four-membered ring including metal ion, similar to the complexes studied here has been reported by Cartwright *et al.*⁸. The stability of the complexes may be due to the π -backbonding to the vacant d-orbitals of sulphur atom.

It has been observed that the substitution of an electronegative atom in the aromatic ring of quinazolones has some effect on the stereochemistry of their complexes. Irrespective of the fact that the substituent at nitrogen-3 is alkyl or aryl and even having no substitution, it has been found that these benzene-substituted-thioquinazolones do not form Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} aquo-complexes as in the case of 3-N-alkylthioquinazolones. The Ni^{II} complexes formed in this case are tetrahedral. The Co^{III} complexes of the benzene-substituted-thioquinazolones do not contain trapped water molecules in the interstitial spacing as in case of the corresponding complexes of the unsubstituted ligands.

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Metal Complexes as Ligand. Binuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Nickel Ethylenediamine Oxalate and Cobalt Ethylenediamine Oxalate

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NICKEL(II) and cobalt(II) ethylenediamine (en), oxalates (Ox), $[\text{Ni/Co}(\text{Ox})\text{en}]$ have been used as 'metal complex ligands' in the synthesis of oxygen-bridged polynuclear alkali metal complexes of the general formula $[\text{M}_b\text{L}\{\text{M}_a(\text{Ox})\text{en}\}]$, where $\text{M}_a = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II} ; $\text{M}_b = \text{Li}$, Na and K; and L = deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N). The